

POLITICAL SCIENCES

FORMATION OF A PERSONNEL RESERVE OF CIVIL SERVANTS IN LOCAL GOVERNMENTS

Ganiev Elyor

*researcher at the Academy of Public Administration
under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan*

ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ КАДРОВОГО РЕЗЕРВА ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫХ СЛУЖАЩИХ В ОРГАНАХ МЕСТНОГО САМОУПРАВЛЕНИЯ

Ганиев Эльёр

*исследователь Академии государственного
управления при Президенте Республики Узбекистан*

Abstract

To implement innovations and improve management efficiency are required new approaches, effective high potential, and highly qualified specialists. For the sustainable development of the territories, the government of the Republic of Uzbekistan is purposefully improving its personnel policy, providing municipal and public services with a strong, highly qualified personnel reserve. We believe that the main task is the scientific substantiation of personnel policy, a high-quality system of work on the formation of a personnel reserve, the development and improvement of the personnel potential of employees, timely updating and assimilation of world experience in local government. Which in turn shows the significance of this article.

Аннотация

Для реализации нововведений и повышения эффективности управления требуются новые подходы, эффективный высокий потенциал, высоко квалифицированные специалисты. Для устойчивого развития территорий правительство Республики Узбекистан целенаправленно совершенствует кадровую политику обеспечивая муниципальную и государственную службы сильным высококвалифицированным кадровым резервом. Полагаем, что главной задачей является научное обоснование кадровой политики, качественная система работы по формированию кадрового резерва, развитие и совершенствование кадрового потенциала сотрудников, своевременное обновление и усвоение мирового опыта в местном самоуправлении. Что в свою очередь показывает значимость данной статьи.

Keywords: personnel reserve, local governments, civil servants, management efficiency, personnel reserve potential, reforms, personnel, principles, monitoring.

Ключевые слова: кадровый резерв, органы местного самоуправления, государственные служащие, эффективность управления, потенциал кадрового резерва, реформы, персонал, принципы, мониторинг.

INTRODUCTION

Global changes are currently taking place in the life of the politics of the Uzbek management system, including views, beliefs, habits, moral values, social roles. And if for some global restructuring is painless, for others it is a huge disaster, leading to restructuring and complete collapse of the established system. To avoid destructuring of the organization and the continuous process of development of the country, personnel reserves are formed. In particular, to attract erudite leaders with more powerful personal potential to improve the efficiency of the country's economic processes. Maximum use of the potential of the personnel reserve serves as an effective tool for strengthening modern Uzbekistan.

The units of effective personnel reserve are state authorities and local governments. However, not only specialists from state and municipal authorities can be in reserve, but also persons from different spheres of society. The main indicators should be high determination and high personal potential of the personnel. In Uzbekistan, events to form a personnel reserve have begun

to take place very often, which reflects the high interest of the state in this issue. The search for new solutions, approaches to the implementation of technologies for managing personnel issues, competent regulatory design, and high-quality work on the formation of a personnel reserve can be the key to the productive solution of many goals and objectives, including the development of human resources.

The main turning point in the system of public civil servants occurred with the adoption on October 3, 2019 of the Presidential Decree "On measures to radically improve personnel policy and the civil service system in the Republic of Uzbekistan."

In accordance with the Resolution, recruitment to the civil service on the basis of an open independent competition began on January 1, 2020 in a pilot mode in certain government bodies, organizations and territories, as well as from January 1, 2021 in all government bodies and organizations. The decree also created the Agency for the Development of Civil Service under

the President, which is the main body in the implementation of personnel policy in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The consequences of these reforms require the presence of highly professional civil servants, whom we can call “new formative cadres”. The main characteristics and competencies of “new education personnel” are:

- a) a person with global thinking;
- b) capable of systematic and creative thinking;
- c) good communication skills;
- d) democratic view;
- e) customer focus;
- f) open to change and flexible.

The secret of a successful organization lies in the implementation of the reproduction of reserve personnel in the state and municipal service.

Technologies described by V.V. Rudov are divided into three groups:

1. Obtaining confidential holistic information about a candidate for a position using methods: assessment, benchmark, testing, interview, discussion.

2. The second group reflects the current personnel needs for the organization, the formation, planning and development of the necessary personnel;

3. Hiring the right specialist for a compatible position in accordance with the regulatory framework.

To obtain competitive, strong personnel and constant turnover and replenishment of personnel, it is an important point to use developed and well-founded personnel technologies, which contributes to the formation of the attraction of highly qualified professionals.

The entire process of forming a personnel reserve is strictly regulated and must be described in the regulations on the personnel reserve and be based on basic principles.

Figure 1. Scheme of work with the personnel reserve in local governments.

A new employee initially undergoes orientation programs (general, special, individual), gets acquainted with the structure of the organization, learns traditions, seminars, and advanced training courses.

Table 1

Principles of forming a personnel reserve

#	Principles	Contents
1	Relevance of the reserve	Need for position
2	Meeting the requirements of the position	Qualification requirements for position
3	Candidate's prospects	Age, management experience in key positions, career dynamics, personal potential
4	Planfulness	Structured and step-by-step personnel development plan

The activity of forming a local government body is very difficult in terms of modeling and forecasting, taking into account all means without exception, both human and material with the possibility of future implementation.

The most powerful candidates, the best of the best, are included in the reserve.

The formation of a professional, powerful personnel reserve is carried out according to the following stages: determining the need for personnel; analysis of personnel capabilities; tender selection for the reserve;

formation of reserves: promotion, training, rotation. Experts in their works define 5 levels of competency expression:

Level 1 - the lowest class of specialists, perform tasks in accordance with their duties;

Level 2 - they perform their work efficiently in accordance with their responsibilities, and in the department as a whole, the line manager, setting tasks, already sees implementation.

Level 3 - middle manager, when setting tasks, he already sees the enterprise as a whole, but sets tasks

from his structural unit, understands his contribution, if he makes his contribution, how it will respond to the overall result.

Level 4 - sees the territory in which the enterprise is located, what benefits it brings to the enterprise. And overcomes obstacles on his own.

Level 5 - expands the territory of the enterprise and helps others improve their quality of life.

The list of personnel reserves in local government bodies mainly recruits applicants from levels 3-4. Recruitment occurs thanks to a commission assessing the specialist's competence. A high level of competencies guarantees results and ways to develop them.

Conclusion

Based on the analysis of scientific literature and the empirical part of practice, the study showed that the management effect depends on the potential of persons occupying key personnel positions and the predicted turnover of personnel with all the ensuing consequences (training, qualifications, compliance with requirements, internships). Analyzing and structuring experience in local self-government, the quality and efficiency of management largely depends on the personal potential of personnel, their timely training depending on the planned position.

A conscious approach to creating a personnel reserve, as the study shows, in most cases is carried out haphazardly, without taking into account the experience of predecessors. Government managers dealing with issues related to personnel have little interest in developing the personnel reserve, however, the presence of a personnel reserve thanks to the development program allows for the rational use of personnel potential for vacant positions.

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